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WHAT IS QUALITY IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION? AN EU PROJECT CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Focusing on the case of a current project funded by the EU ERASMUS+ Programme, this paper will explore the question - *what is quality in engineering education?* The project called EXTEND is seeking to develop the next generation of Engineering Educators in the Russian Federation and Tajikistan and is supported by partners from Romania, Latvia, Portugal and the UK.

It is very apparent that when we explore quality in engineering education it can mean different things to different people. As the diversity of higher education increases in terms of students, teachers, courses, modes of delivery etc, now is an appropriate time to revisit and explore this topic as it is invariably the engineering educators who are tasked with reconciling the, often competing, requirements.

Using data collected during the course of the EXTEND Project and considering the wider engineering education context, the authors will seek to offer suggestions as to how the ideas of what constitutes 'quality' can be embedded within courses aimed at developing the next generation of engineering educators. This will help to ensure that when designing and delivering courses the outcomes for all stakeholders are realised.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Building on some of the ideas explored by Clark et al that focused on the features of quality in funded engineering education projects [1], this paper uses a current EU Project as the case within which to explore the quality of engineering education itself. By understanding what constitutes 'high quality', the aim of the work is to start to formulate a framework within which institutions wishing to develop their engineering education expertise can systematically address the key areas that will have the most impact. The Capacity Building Project that forms the subject of this work is focused on the development of engineering education in countries that are not as mature in their understanding of what 'high quality' requires.

2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE

In earlier work it was stated that to understand what we mean by quality, the context we are considering is of considerable importance. In this paper we are focusing on the engineering higher education context in the global space which often separates into two dominant considerations, Quality Assurance and Quality Enhancement. Williams argues that they are 'integral parts of the same process' [2] although their purity is increasingly contaminated as quality becomes associated with measures such as rankings [3] or content [4]. This perceived 'tension between QA and QE' has been explored in the literature with measures to capture the synergy Williams alludes to being proposed through self assessment [5] and collaborative QE [6].

Quality improvements can be prompted through many channels other than policy and process – students [7], alumni [8] and industry [9] are three such examples. It needs to be acknowledged that each of these stakeholder groups will likely have different perspectives as to what constitutes quality and how important each element is [10].

Despite the structured QA approaches in many western countries [11] [12], challenges exist across the world. On the positive side, in seeking to improve the quality of higher education in Afghanistan, a QA framework is seen as being integral to 'organisational sensemaking' and the all important support of senior leadership [13]. Russia (one of the partner countries in EXTEND) has been grappling with the challenges with respect to engineering education for many years. Debates about a 'National Doctrine' in 2012 [14] have struggled to realise significant change with recent authors suggesting there remain 'quality and relevance' issues in Russian institutions [15].

Acknowledging the need for change to improve quality is an important first step. The passive approach to engineering education in India is being challenged by models such as flipped learning [16]. In Nigeria, the recognition that quality will improve only with better able teaching staff is similarly important [17]. The recent work by Campbell et al suggests that an important feature of student success in engineering education is the development of a 'growth mindset' [18]. A mindset that is flexible and resilient in the face of change. Much engineering education today remains didactic in nature and far removed from the high quality, active and engaging approaches that will aid the development of such a mindset.

3 CONTEXT

The context of this paper is an EU funded ERASMUS+ project that is in the last year of its work. The EXTEND project is focused on modernising the approaches used in teaching engineering in Russia and Tajikistan and, through this, developing the educators engaged in the teaching [19]. The quality of education is central to this project, especially when the objective is to develop in each of the Russian and Tajik universities (4 in each country), an active, respected and sustainable Centre for engineering educator training. The challenge is what form the Centres and their work should take in order to be effective in realising high quality engineering education in each of the institutions. Following the events of the last 2 years, the latter stage of the project will also seek to capture the role of blended learning in each Centre and the associated quality considerations.

4 APPROACH TO THE STUDY

Data collection has been taking place throughout the project in various forms and this paper draws together two threads of this work. At an early stage of the project the Centres were asked to complete a Business Model Canvas [20] and develop a clear and compelling vision that would focus on excellence and sustainability. This initial work conducted in 2018 has been revisited throughout the project and will be contrasted with the data collected for the last face-to-face project meeting in 2020.

The data collection is being guided by the Quality Plan for the project. The current phase of the work is focused on establishing the quality and value of the EXTEND Centres and will draw on a range of data sources. To date these have been the Project Team Members who have been with the project since its outset. It is this work that is reported here.

In completing this work over the next year these data sources will be extended to include, but not be limited to, interviews with Centre staff, users and beneficiaries (e.g. students and university administration), usage data for the Centres, a review of the Centre spaces and the facilities they offer, scrutiny of the documentation and resources produced as part of the Centres' operation, evidence of the Centres' visibility and reach both within the host institution and on the national stage and finally observations on how the individual EXTEND Centres are co-operating with each other.

5 RESULTS

5.1 5.1 Data Collection Point 1 – Bucharest 2018

Prior to and during the Project Meeting in Bucharest in 2018, each Centre was asked to complete a Canvas. An example for one of the partner universities is shown in Figure 1.

Business Model Canvas of Partner University's EXTEND Center				
Key partners	Key activities	Value Proposition	Customer relationships	Customers segments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Industries ✓ Ministry of Education and Science ✓ Ministry of Industry ✓ Employees/Companies ✓ EXTEND Partners ✓ Local Authorities ✓ Ministry of Labour Migration and Employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Teaching ✓ Consulting ✓ Training ✓ Programming ✓ Connecting, ✓ Analyzing and Publishing results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Recognition ✓ Placement Opportunity ✓ Unified Centre ✓ Increase research opportunities ✓ Distance Learning ✓ MOOCs ✓ Virtual Mobility ✓ Designing New Courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Ministry's permission ✓ Rector's instructions ✓ Volunteering ✓ Involving interested and motivated Staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Teachers ✓ Students ✓ Industries ✓ Partners ✓ Universities ✓ Community
	<p>Key resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Intellectual Capital ✓ Advanced Equipment ✓ Unified Centre ✓ Significant Technical Opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ International Visibility and Mobility ✓ Authentic Practices that will benefit Students 	<p>Channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Website ✓ Mass Media ✓ Social Media ✓ Former Students ✓ Student Union ✓ Conferences and Seminars ✓ Personal interaction / Networks ✓ Journals 	
Cost structure		Revenue Stream		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Fixed cost ✓ Variable costs ✓ Software Development ✓ Space for the Centre ✓ Equipping and Maintaining the Centre ✓ Time ✓ Opportunity cost 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Project funding and extension ✓ Co-funding from University ✓ Licensing ✓ Outsourcing ✓ Partnerships 		

Fig. 1. Sample Business Model Canvas

Many of the elements identified in this sample Canvas were replicated in those produced by the other Centres. During the meeting these documents were critiqued and the Centres were challenged to explore their ideas further with a particular focus on 4 questions that would help to realise excellence and sustainability for each Centre. The questions were:

WHY? What is the purpose of the EXTEND Centre, particularly its vision?

WHAT? What will be the portfolio of activities for the Centre?

HOW? How will the Centre achieve its objectives? What are the resource requirements?

WHO? Who will be essential in making the vision a reality?

A thematic analysis was performed on the Canvas' and the results of the critique. In doing this, with the focus on excellence and sustainability, 4 main themes were identified – People, Portfolio of Activity, Place and Supporting Environment. These will be explored one by one.

All of the Centres viewed the project as a significant opportunity for their institutions and country. In terms of **People**, the key aspirations were to create a motivated, high quality and recognised teaching workforce. Linking the benefits to ongoing employability and lifelong learning were highlighted, as was the need to explore a form of certification to accompany the activity taking place within a Centre.

In terms of the **Portfolio**, the Centres took a very broad view of what would be needed. Key features were the need for virtual offerings as well as classroom based, courses that were relevant and authentic and delivered using a variety of teaching approaches. Quality Assurance was mentioned but for most the view was that the Centre should be about Quality Enhancement and should have a scholarly and 'scientific' basis, not be too practice focused. The opportunity to introduce latest thinking in learning and teaching along with an industry view was also viewed as important. Experience sharing was singled out for particular mention.

Having a dedicated and appropriately equipped **Place** was seen as essential. Each Centre saw this as a way to create visibility and to make a statement about the importance of the work to the wider institution. This was extended to suggest the need for a variety of communication strategies on an institutional, national and international level to enable the Centre to connect to a wider network of possibilities. These possibilities were seen as an important feature for the Centre sustainability.

The final theme is that of a **Supporting Environment**. It was felt that the support of University Administrations and Government Ministries was particularly important for sustainability and for the Centres to be influential. This would enable future funding to be explored and realised extending to industry and other partners who may wish to co-create and engage in activities with a Centre.

5.2 Data Collection Point 2 – Warwick 2020

For the Warwick Meeting the Centres were asked to explore the progress made in the setting up of their facilities and their steps towards providing an environment for quality engineering education to be realised. Each Centre had focused on the setting up of one teacher education course as its core activity. Around this the supporting activities to create the Centre and realise the vision were being actioned.

The focus of this data collection activity were 3 questions:

What have been the positive points of the work so far?

What points have you identified that will be the focus of improvements?

What are your ideas for the future in order to make your Centre sustainable?

Focusing on these questions, the responses from the different Centres have been analysed using the 4 themes identified from the work in 2018. It should be stated at the outset that at the point of this data collection each Centre had been established and the initial course design had been created and piloted.

The **People** attending the courses clearly viewed the work in a positive light. Teacher training based on latest thinking was a new experience for many and their engagement was positive in all cases. The enthusiasm came through in the post-

course reviews with participants having their ‘eyes opened to many new possibilities’. There were challenges in getting some ideas accepted yet the idea that the Institution was consciously investing in its staff and the opportunity to share experiences were welcomed. Some universities have sought to embed the courses in a formal teacher development programme but this was the exception. It also became apparent that mixed cohorts of teachers and PhD students were a challenge as each had a different starting knowledge.

As may be expected, with the focus on course development, the **Portfolio** theme was most dominant in the responses. The teachers developing the courses for their colleagues to experience worked hard to embrace the latest ideas from across the globe, making the learning authentic, active, relevant and of high quality within the cultural environment they were used to. All saw the piloted courses as a first step and embraced the idea of continuous improvement. What was clear was that in order for the courses to be taken seriously by the learners, they needed to be developed on a solid ‘scientific’ base and at times this deflected the resulting design away from its pedagogical objectives until the review process highlighted the challenge. Obtaining appropriate supporting and reference materials in the native language was also a commonly referred to problem.

One of the features of the project was the realisation from the outset that a physical **Place** for the Centre would be essential for its success. All of the Centres had achieved this presence by the time of the data collection and it was clear that this had created a real excitement within the Project Team for each Centre as well as in the wider institution. The associated visibility on the institution website and the scheduling of Opening Events had all helped to embed the Centre and what it is about into the institutional environment.

Of the 4 themes it is perhaps the **Supporting Environment** where there was least evidence of the success that will be needed to ensure the Centres are sustainable. There is still anxiety about funding, the support of the Administration and the ability to create a place for the Centres within the individual institutional cultures. Where the Centres had linked into wider institutional initiatives such as teacher development programmes, e-learning projects and quality enhancement drivers, the possibility for longer term success are more likely. The Centres all intend to create a network in which sharing and co-operation will be enabled that will help to sustain the life of the individual Centres. It is this last point that will form the final stage of the work to ensure quality engineering education is realised in each of the 8 partner universities in Russia and Tajikistan.

6 DISCUSSION

The analysis has identified 4 themes around which the development of quality engineering education can be enabled in the 8 partner universities, each with a newly formed EXTEND Centre. Although progress was made with respect to the development of the course and event portfolio in the designated spaces the Centres had been allocated, much work needs to be undertaken to ensure the path to high quality engineering education is maintained. This will, to a large extent, be facilitated by the local Administration, as the success of each Centre and the realisation of its

vision will require top level support. The Centres are a new idea within both Russia and Tajikistan and the prevailing culture is likely to not be fully supportive. That suggests the value of the courses, the networking and the impact on people needs to be captured to provide evidence to support cases for funding and resource.

Even in EU countries, Centres like the EXTEND Centres often experience cycles of support and threat that undermine attempts to enhance teaching quality. Engineering as a subject often experiences challenges either due to its attractiveness to potential students or its relevance to industry employers. Against this backdrop, it is even more important that engineering education develops a reputation for being both engaging and high quality if universities are to develop for the engineering talent for the future. Hence the success of teacher development and Centres like those discussed here is crucial.

In considering a potential framework within which to establish the success and sustainability of an individual Centre, the initial thoughts are around exploring the following 7 criteria

- Clarity of Purpose
- Funding
- High level Support
- Space
- Partnerships
- Innovative ideas
- Capable Teachers

These are consistent with the results of the thematic analysis but presented in a slightly different way to capture a little more of the detail from the responses. The final evaluation work will consider a rating statement for each EXTEND Centre based on these criteria as a way to helping them to develop a sustainable future.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This is a work in progress that is exploring how to create the right environment for quality engineering education. The benefits and challenges of setting up dedicated Centres are being examined as the project progresses. The culture and academic traditions of the institutions where the Centres are located are an important consideration and one that will be explored further as the sustainability of the Centres is studied.

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